

DIGITAL IMAGE CORRELATION AND FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS APPLIED TO FIBER-REINFORCED COMPOSITES AT THE MICRO-SCALE

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ABSTRACT

Digital image correlation (DIC) is a widely employed technique to study deformation of fiber-reinforced composites at the macro and meso-levels. It is, however, rarely applied at the micro-level although deformation analysis of the microstructure is of great interest in the field of composites. This is mainly attributed to practical difficulties related to creation of a nano-scale speckle pattern as well as the experimental set-up. The challenge is to combine DIC with SEM, where imaging involves noise, the gray intensity level of microstructure can be uniform over large areas, and it is difficult to maintain the observation window fixed during loading.

The current study aims to address these challenges and enhance the methodology for real-time strain mapping of composites at the micro-scale. A large effort of the work is dedicated to deposition of a high-quality nano-scale random speckle pattern, of which the adequacy is assessed through a strain deviation analysis. The DIC parameters are optimized for the study zone. The methodology is applied to a fiber-reinforced composite loaded under transverse three-point bending inside an ESEM.

The innovations in this methodology necessitate its validation against more reliable methods. For this, a finite element model of the study zone is created with boundary conditions taken from the experiment. An acceptable level of agreement was observed between experimentally measured and numerically predicted displacement/strain maps. For the studied case, DIC could correctly capture the mean strain, display the effect of microstructure heterogeneity, show the lowest strains inside fibers, and finally detect some of the strain concentrations in the matrix between fibers. Some small-scale strain concentrations e.g. those in between touching fibers, however, could not be detected. Overall, it was concluded that the methodology can be considered as a promising and dependable technique for strain mapping at the micro-scale.

1 INTRODUCTION

Digital image correlation (DIC) is a well-known optical technique for measuring the deformation in a set of consecutive images, taken from the surface of a deforming material. It has been widely employed for analysis of the deformation behavior of different materials, particularly composites, at macro- and meso-level [1-3]. Since the heterogeneity of Fiber-Reinforced Composites (FRCs) does exist at the scale of fibers, i.e. micro-scale, the deformation analysis at this scale is of great importance. Thus, the need for application of DIC at micro-scale (μ DIC) becomes significant for these materials. Moreover, μ DIC has the potential to support the mechanical study of novel composites such as nano-engineered fiber-reinforced composites and composites with multiphase matrices, where the effect of modifications is most pronounced at the micro-scale [4-7].

DIC can be explained in three steps: 1) creating virtual and small grids, which are called subsets, on each image 2) correlating images in order to locate each subset on each image 3) assigning a displacement vector for each subset in each image by comparing the initial and final positions of the subsets [8]. Strain maps can be built by differentiating the resulting displacement. The correlation process distinguishes each subset by the gray intensity pattern inside it. Therefore, it is essential that each subset should hold a unique gray intensity pattern. This pattern is either the natural material texture or an artificial random speckle pattern produced on material surface [9]. The scale of DIC is defined by the length scale of the images that will be processed. For applying DIC at the micro-scale, the length scale of images should be micro, which means they must be acquired through microscopy.

In contrast to metals, for which the application of μ DIC has been examined since late 90s [10-14], composite materials have been rarely explored through μ DIC. In a scarce study, Canal et al. [15], tried to investigate the deformation behavior of a unidirectional (UD) E-glass/epoxy composite under transverse compression through μ DIC. In this analysis, the average composite strain of the region of interest was accurately calculated. However, at high magnifications (2000x, and 6000x), the average strain in each phase could not be calculated accurately. They explained that deformation gradient at the fiber/matrix interface is high, but since DIC calculate the strains by taking the derivate of the displacements over a small strain window, the high strain mismatch at the interface is smoothed out. Thus, DIC does not result in precise strains for interfaces with high mechanical mismatch.

The present study is planned to employ μ DIC to develop a methodology for performing real-time displacement and strain investigation of a FRC at the micro-scale. The technique is performed on an example of UD glass fiber/epoxy composite, loaded in transverse three-point bending inside an ESEM chamber. The main challenge is to overcome the large areas with uniform gray intensity level on the microstructure. This is achieved by producing a nano-scale random speckle pattern on the surface of the composite. As the developed technique is a novel approach, finite element analysis (FEA), as a common and reliable technique, is employed for comparison and validation of the results.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Composite material

A UD glass fiber/epoxy composite is used. This FRC, produced by vacuum infusion in form of plates, was studied in [16]. The average values for fiber diameter, plate thickness, and fiber volume fraction are 17 μ m, 1.9 mm, and 61.9 %, respectively. The Young's moduli of the glass fiber and epoxy matrix are 81 and 3 GPa, and the Poisson's ratios are 0.22 and 0.30, respectively. The plate is cut into 68.0 \times 8.0 \times 1.9 mm³ specimens. The fibers are aligned in the width direction. The transverse surfaces of the specimens are grinded by SiC papers (320, 800, 1200, and 4000 grit, consecutively) and polished by a diamond slurry of 1- μ m particle size, followed by an oxide polishing suspension.

2.2 Speckle patterning

As explained, DIC requires a random pattern on the surface of material. The SEM micrograph indicates that no natural patterns exist on the surface of the glass fiber/epoxy composite (Figure 1a). Thus, a nano-scale random speckle pattern needs to be artificially produced. One approach in speckle patterning at this scale is deposition of nano-particles [17, 18]. A powder with appropriate particle size and high contrast with fibers and matrix should be selected. Considering these parameters, an alumina powder (*TM-DAR* series of *TAIMICRON*) with the average particle size of 220 nm is chosen.

The main challenge in depositing nano-particles is aggregation. Aggregates lead to significant errors in DIC since they are large areas with uniform gray intensity level which cannot be properly correlated. Additionally, they cover the underlying surface in large areas and this interferes with tracking the deformation of the whole microstructure. To inhibit aggregation, a dispersing agent can be used. *DARVAN-CN* (a trademark of *R.T. Vanderbilt Holding Company, Inc.* for ammonium polymethacrylate), which is used as a dispersant for stabilizing alumina suspensions, is employed.

In order to achieve suitable dispersion and distribution of particles, several deposition trails were performed. In each trial, a water-base suspension of alumina particles is prepared and applied to the polished surface of a specimen. Then, the surface is dried in ambient air. The details of variables in each trail are described in Table 1. Micrographs taken from the deposited surface in each trail are shown in Figure 1. It is evident that the final trail results in well-dispersed and evenly distributed particles (Figure 1f), which can be accepted as a suitable random speckle pattern for μ DIC.

Trail	Alumina wt. %	Dispersing agent	Ultrasonication + magnetic stirring	Deposition repeated
1	1	-	no	no
2	1	-	yes	no
3	1	DARVAN-CN	yes	no
4	0.1	DARVAN-CN	yes	no
5	0.05	DARVAN-CN	yes	yes

Table 1: Deposition trails performed for achieving a suitable speckle pattern.

Figure 1: SEM images of a (a) bare surface and (b)-(f) speckled surfaces in trial 1-5, respectively.

2.3 Evaluation of the speckle pattern quality

The DIC accuracy depends enormously on the quality of the speckle pattern, which is how well it can be used in distinctive subset recognition. For evaluation of the speckle pattern, a technique called *strain deviation analysis* is established in this study. In this technique, a micrograph of the surface with the speckle pattern (reference image) is virtually deformed (in several steps) in an image editing software. Then, DIC is applied to the virtually deformed images. The DIC resulting mean strain and the deviation of strain in the last step of deformation are evaluated. Since the (virtual) deformation is applied uniformly to the reference image, the resulting strain should be uniform all over the image. Any heterogeneity in the resulting strain is, therefore, the correlation error due to imperfect speckle pattern. Thus, strain standard deviation can be assessed as a measure of correlation error. It should be noted that virtually deforming an image might introduce some errors in DIC, but as long as the technique is used in comparison, it can be reliable (since same error exist in both cases).

The strain deviation analysis is performed on two micrographs; one from a poorly-speckled and the other from a well-speckled surface. The suitable speckle image is taken in ‘high-definition’ mode, with the resolution of 1424×968 pixel², while the other image has the resolution of 712×484 pixel². The virtual deformation is applied by extending the length of the reference images, while the width is constant. The total deformation of both images corresponds to a value of 0.01059 for the horizontal component of the Lagrangian strain. DIC is applied to the (virtually) deformed images of each pattern using *Vic-2D 2009* software (*Correlated Solutions*). The sizes of subset and step (DIC parameters that are explained further) are set to 60 and 2 pixels for the suitable pattern, and 30 pixels and 1 pixel for the poor pattern, respectively. Although the DIC resulting mean strain at the last step is calculated accurately for both patterns, higher strain heterogeneity for the poor pattern is observed in the resulting strain maps in Figure 2a, b. Moreover, this figure shows the resulting strain along a vertical line shown on both maps (Figure 2c).

Figure 2: Effect of the pattern quality on the accuracy of DIC: strain maps for a (a) poorly-speckled and (b) well-speckled specimen, (c) strain along the straight line shown on the two strain maps.

2.4 Evaluation of DIC parameters

The correlation accuracy depends on correlation resolution and correlation error. Correlation resolution is defined by the details that the DIC resulting maps hold. Correlation error refers to when the results of the correlation are wrong for one or more pixels (e.g. due to areas with imperfect speckle pattern). Thus, high correlation accuracy is ensured by a combination of high resolution with low correlation error. Aside from the quality of speckle pattern, DIC accuracy can be manipulated through several parameters, among which subset, step, and filter size are significant.

Subsets are the virtual grids created on the image and acting as correlation units. The larger the subsets are, the lower the correlation resolution is. This is because DIC averages the displacement over subsets, and for large subsets, local variations may not be accurately detected. However, larger subsets hold more speckles, and can be distinguished more precisely. Therefore, the subset size should be a compromise between small values, which provide more detailed measurements, but also higher correlation error, and large values, which decrease the error. Step size defines the spacing between successive subsets. Lower step size indicates analyzing more pixels and providing a more detailed correlation (higher resolution), which also may result in identifying more imperfectly-speckled areas (higher correlation error). Hence, the subset size should be chosen similarly in a trade-off manner. The last studied parameter is filter size. It is the size of a smoothing filter window, by which the displacement is smoothed, before calculating the strain, to reduce the measurement noise. Small smoothing windows results in better spatial resolution, and detect strain concentrations clearly, but more noise in strain as well. The same trade-off scenario applies for this parameter also.

For choosing suitable values for subset, step, and filter size, the strain deviation analysis technique is used. Eight DIC processes with different sets of parameters are applied to the 15 virtually deformed images from the suitable speckle pattern. The strain mean and standard deviation of the last (15th) step of each process are presented in Table 2. It shows that mean strain is very precisely calculated for all of the parameter sets. Moreover, it confirms the above statements on correlation error. The higher the values of subset, step, and filter size are, the lower the standard deviation (correlation error) is. Nevertheless, even for the least values of the parameters, the standard deviation is rather small. Therefore, the values of 2 pixels and 5 data points are chosen for step and filter size, respectively. For subset size selection, taking into account that subsets have to be large enough to include a sufficient number of speckles [19], the 60-pixel subset seems to ensure high DIC accuracy for this pattern. The investigated subsets are displayed on the suitable pattern micrograph in Figure 3c. In sum, the optimized values for subset, step, and filter size are 60 pixels, 2 pixels, and 5 data points, respectively. It should be noted that in the DIC strain map of the last step (holding a virtual strain of 0.01059) with these optimum parameters, the maximum ‘local’ deviation is 0.00223.

Subset size (pixel)	Step size (pixel)	Filter size (data point)	Strain mean	Strain standard deviation
40	5	15	0.01060	0.00027
60	5	15	0.01059	0.00024
80	5	15	0.01059	0.00021
100	5	15	0.01060	0.00015
60	10	15	0.01060	0.00015
60	2	15	0.01059	0.00050
60	2	11	0.01059	0.00064
60	2	5	0.01059	0.00085

Table 2: Effect of DIC parameters on the resulting horizontal strain at the final (15th) step of the virtual deformation on the well-speckled image. The applied strain is 0.01059.

2.5 *In-situ* imaging of the deforming material

Achieving an appropriate nano-scale speckle pattern and optimum values for DIC parameters through the virtual deformation analysis, the real deformation is applied to the well-speckled specimen. The deformation should take place inside an electron microscope. It is provided by a mini-tester stage (*Deben UK Limited*) that has the ability to be installed inside an ESEM chamber (*FEI/Philips XL30 ESEM FEG*). The mini-tester can apply transverse three-point bending to the specimen. For that, the specimen is placed on the bending stage with fibers transversely aligned to the loading. A study zone with a suitable distribution of fibers inside matrix is chosen. The study zone is located in the middle of the tensile edge (Figure 3), so that the deformation is the maximum and the movement of the region is the minimum. The whole analysis is carried out on this study zone.

Figure 3: The study zone chosen for strain mapping, shown (a) schematically on the specimen in three-point bending, (b) on the specimen cross-section, (c) at the working magnification (1000x).

In order to evaluate the adequacy of microscopy for μ DIC, 4 successive micrographs were taken from the study zone in 30-second intervals, without any deformation (rigid body). In addition, 5 other micrographs were taken while the imaging window was a bit re-positioned over the study zone, also without any deformation (rigid body motion). DIC were applied to these two sets of micrographs, separately. Since no deformation was exerted during imaging, DIC should show no resulting strain. However, for both sets of micrographs, small deviations from zero do exist in all strain component maps. These deviations may be due to imaging distortions and noise [20, 22], and vibrations of the test stage. The spurious strains are in the same order of magnitude in both DIC processes. The maximum local strain in the maps is around 0.005, and the maximum mean strain is roughly 0.0005.

Three-point bending, using the mini-tester with a 50-N load cell and speed of 0.1 mm/min, starts on the specimen and each 30 seconds stops for taking a micrograph from the study zone. The imaging takes 40 seconds and the force drop in this time interval is below 0.05 N. The loading proceeds until 60 micrographs with the resolution of 1424×968 pixel² (125×85 μm^2 at the magnification of 1000x) are taken. The final micrograph corresponds to the applied force of nearly 26 N, and the bending deflection of 1.7 mm.

DIC is applied to the micrographs, employing the optimized parameters. The resulting mean strain is 0.00911 for the last (59th) step. The maximum mean strain, in rigid body correlation, was roughly 0.0005, while the resulting standard deviation with the optimum parameters was 0.00085. Moreover, the maximum local strain in the DIC maps of real-deformation is around 0.02580 (see subsection 3.2), which is higher than that of the rigid body correlation (that is 0.00545). Accordingly, errors from microscopy are not very significant for the areas with high local strains. However, they may become prominent for areas with absolute strain values near 0.00545 or less. The false local strains can have two sources: 1) microscopy deficiencies 2) speckle pattern imperfection.

2.6 Finite element modeling

A finite element model of the study zone is developed so that the DIC results can be compared and validated by FEA predictions. The model simulates the microstructure of the study zone as a two-dimensional problem under plane strain assumptions. The geometry and distribution of fibers in the model are the same as the study zone. The elastic mechanical properties of the fibers and matrix are assigned. Boundary conditions (BCs) also need to simulate the same loading condition as the real deformation. Applying the loading condition, which is experimentally measured through DIC, to the edges of the model, the deformation inside the edges can be compared with DIC results. BCs are, thus, extracted from DIC resulting displacements at the last (59th) step, and exerted to the model edges.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results from both methods, DIC and FEA, are reported for the last step of the deformation (the 60th image). Moreover, for FEA, the same coordinate system as DIC is defined to allow comparison between the maps.

3.1 Displacement analysis

Figure 4a, b show horizontal displacement maps, resulted from DIC and FEA, respectively. Likewise, the vertical displacement maps measured and predicted from DIC and FEA are displayed in Figure 4c, d. A high level of agreement can be observed between DIC and FEA maps. In the results of both methods, the trend of increase in displacement is similar and also the neighboring fibers tend to move together. DIC could correctly recognize that displacement occurs more in the horizontal direction than in the vertical one (based on the difference in the variation range of the maps). This is due to the x-direction tensile mode of loading in the bottom edge of the specimen.

Figure 4: Horizontal displacement maps resulted from (a) DIC and (b) FEA and vertical displacement maps resulted from (c) DIC and (d) FEA.

3.2 Strain analysis

The mean strain at the last step, calculated from DIC data and FEA analysis is 0.00911 and 0.00902, respectively. The maps of strain components, resulted from DIC and FEA for the last step of deformation, are depicted in Figure 5. DIC maps (Figure 5a, c) show that the fibers are isolated from matrix, which is due to their high stiffness. The high local strains on fibers, however, might be the result of microscopy deficiencies and errors from correlation process, which become significant for areas with low levels of strain. The highest difference between fibers and matrix strain is observed in the horizontal component map (Figure 5a). The absolute value of local strains is also the highest in this map. Moreover, the positive horizontal strain and negative vertical strain, almost all over the matrix, demonstrate that DIC could correctly validate that the study zone is, in general, expanding in the x-direction and shrinking in the y-direction.

Figure 5: Horizontal strain maps resulted from (a) DIC and (b) FEA and vertical strain maps resulted from (c) DIC and (d) FEA. White circles are drawn around the similarly detected strain concentrations.

In order to allow the comparison between DIC and FEA maps, the limits in the legend of the FEA maps are restricted to those from the DIC data. The difference in the legend range is mostly because of the deformation smoothing. DIC could hardly detect small-scale strain concentrations (e.g. in between touching fibers) since the strains are calculated over a small strain window [15]. In FEA horizontal map (Figure 5b), strain is high between neighboring fibers, almost aligned in the x-direction, and the highest between almost-touching fibers. In contrast, the horizontal strain is low between adjacent fibers, aligned in the y-direction. DIC could detect one of the horizontal strain concentrations very well (encircled in Figure 5a, b). The other strain concentrations, however, are not identified probably due to their small size. The other difference is that the horizontal strain map from FEA looks more uniform than that from DIC. As discussed, the strain inhomogeneity in DIC strain maps is a result of microscopy deficiencies and correlation errors. Similar to horizontal strain, FEA shows the highest vertical strains in areas between adjacent fibers (Figure 5d). DIC identifies most of these vertical strain concentrations.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The application of micro-scale DIC to FRCs is studied in order to accomplish real-time micro-scale analysis of deformation in this class of materials. The dependency of μ DIC on the random speckle pattern quality is shown. A high-quality nano-scale speckle pattern is achieved by deposition of alumina particles on the composite surface. The DIC parameters are optimized for the speckle pattern. Applying a mechanical loading to the speckled composite inside an electron microscope and performing DIC to the micrographs, a set of displacement and strain maps are achieved. The results are in agreement with micromechanics of FRCs. Additionally, the FEA, which is performed with validation purpose, confirms most of the DIC results. The limitations in the methodology are the weakness in detecting small-scale strain concentrations and also local spurious strains, which are due to microscopy deficiencies and correlation errors. Therefore, further improvements can be made in order to achieve more accurate strain maps. Firstly, the possibility of reducing subset size should be investigated. Secondly, limiting the effect of microscopy distortions and noise in deformation micrographs can be more investigated.

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